

1 **Hypermethylation of homeobox genes is associated with rapid death in TNBC.**

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6 We studied genes expressed in the tumor that influence survival of the host in humans with triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) using whole genome methylation analysis of the primary tumor in patients based on the number of days the patient survived following diagnosis (overall survival). Multiple homeobox genes were among those identified as most differentially methylated in the TNBC primary tumor. These homeobox factors included *PAX7*, *HOXC12*, as well as *EN1* and *EN2*. We recently identified homeobox genes as determinative factors in transformation and in relapse and resistance. These data reinforce an essential role for homeobox transcription factors in supporting tumor survival in a manner that antagonizes host survival.

7 Citations

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11 1. Abate-Shen, C., 2002. Deregulated homeobox gene expression in cancer: cause or consequence?. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 2(10), pp.777-785.